

The ICT And Functional Education for the Adolescent

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Abstract

Global trends are driven by technology, especially the information and communication technology (ICT). Various electronic devices, such as the computer, printer, scanner, satellites, microwaves, Internet and e-mail are used to process and store information for use when the need arises. Business in private and public sectors are now technology based. This calls for the need for functional education for the adolescent so as to enable him acquire the necessary skills needed for productivity in the labour market in this world of competitive technology. This paper explores the concepts of ICT, functional education and the adolescent. It outlines and discusses the importance of ICT in engineering functional education for the adolescent. It recommends among other things that information and communication technology (ICT) should be made compulsory subject in all schools and Colleges.

Introduction

The world has gone advanced in sophisticated technology. Of paramount importance is the use of information and communication technology (ICT). ICT which is a relatively new field of computing is the use of any computer based tool, electronic device or equipment to collect, process and store information for future use. The information stored could be used to support and manage the information needs of an organization, corporation, industry and institutions. ICT is the fastest growing form of technology in the labour market. Employers of labour need graduates and school leavers who are ICT literate. In view of this, there is need for functional education for the adolescent so as to enable him acquire the requisite knowledge and skills needed in using ICT resources. This will make the adolescent not to be bypassed or dropped by the new technology in the labour market. Where the adolescent has adequate knowledge of ICT, he or she becomes a hot-cake in the labour market.

The acquisition of requisite skill is a means of increasing the productive power of a person. With the increasing rate of industrialization in the country, human resources with the ICT skills and abilities are required. Therefore, there is need to lay good ICT foundation for the adolescent while he is in the school so that when he comes out he will be a productive member of the society.

Social vices and juvenile delinquent acts such as stealing, pick-pocketing, abortion and teenage pregnancy etc will not be for him or her. In the words of Fanyisetan and Peebly (1989) one of the grave consequences of teenage pregnancy is child abandonment or baby dumping. In order to meet the challenges and demands of the new technologies and operational skills, the adolescent needs functional education. That is education for skills development and productivity, education for living, and education for self-reliance or self-employment.

What is ICT?

ICT stands for information and communication Technology. ICT is a relatively new field of computing and it is extremely a complex one. It can be defined as the science of information processing which deals with the use of computers, and other electronic devices to collect, processes, store, retrieve and transmit or disseminate information to any part of the world. It can also be understood as the science of collecting and processing information, facts, values, skills, thoughts, text, graphics, pictures, card, sounds, news and all other forms of data in digital form for dissemination in both immediate and remote locations. For instance, in Bank transactions, the Automated teller machine (ATM) is used in both immediate and remote locations. According to Hall and Smith (1991). ICT is the use of electronic and telecommunication devices namely computer and terminals, satellites, microwaves modems, Digital pagers and wireless application protocols in the collection, processing and dissemination of information. In the words of Uzoigwe (2001), ICT involves all the technologies employed in order to facilitate the collection, storage, retrieval and communication of information by the fastest means. The National Policy on Education (FRN, 2004) recognizes ICT as a product of technological change and as an innovation in education.

Concept of Functional Education.

Throughout the world, the concept of functional education is made in direct response to the needs of the society. In Nigeria, the major factor that triggered off the concept of functional education was the inadequacies in the colonial education curriculum. The curriculum then was on liberal arts and it kept on producing subservient Nigerians who worked as gardeners stewards, catechists etc. The labour market/world of work then ended in white-collar jobs. There was the need to overhaul the curriculum to reflect science and technology for self-reliance of both the individual and the nation. Again, the concept of functional education rose out of the demands of modern technology on our rapidly changing society.

Functional education can be defined as the skillful and productive education. It is the education that enables the people to use their creative ingenuity, technical skills, abilities and competences to be self-reliant and to improve their standard of living. It is the education that encourages initiative and self-effort in making a person a productive member of the society. It is the education that makes a person an efficient and creative producer rather than parasitic consumer. It could also be understood as the education for self-reliance and self-sustenance. According to Ukeje (1957), functional education is the education for self-reliance and for living. Berstecher (1985) defines functional education as the means through which the scientific and

technological requisites are to be fulfilled so as to enable the people tap the materials around them and manage their own economic and social affairs. According to Anyanwu (1987), functional education is the education that triggers off economic development; and trains various occupational groups to improve their working efficiency and to increase their productivity. UNESCO (1964) pointed out that, functional education is the acquisition of the essential knowledge and skills that enable a person engage in all those activities for the development of himself and his community.

Who is an Adolescent?

The concept of adolescent has psychological, legal and technical definitions. From psychological point of view, an adolescent is a teenager that is, a young person of above 12 years maturing and moving from the end of childhood to the beginning of adulthood. According to Child (1977), an adolescent is a young person facing the period of life span when the physiological and psychological processes are in transition between puberty and maturity. Sigmund Freud (1856-1939) defined an adolescent as a sexually driven and conflicted young person. Hall (1963) remarked that, an adolescent is a young person facing the period of "storm and stress" that is, a turbulent time changed with conflicting and moody state, thoughts, feelings and actions oscillate between happiness and sadness, consent and humility. From legal and technical point of view, in Nigeria for instance, an adolescent IS a young person under 18 years of age. Technically, an adolescent is a juvenile. The Osborn's Concise Law Dictionary defines a juvenile offender as a young offender. Child (1977) defines a juvenile as a young person under 18 years of age that indulges in delinquent act or any behaviour to which the more senior members of a society object.

Some characteristics of the adolescents are:

- i. Sexual maturation in boys starts with development of baritone voice, enlargement of testicles and increase in the size and length of penis,
- ii. Sexual maturation in girls starts with development of the breasts, hairs in private parts, rounding of the hips and menstruation experience,
- iii. Increase relationship with peers,
- iv. The search for emotional, social and economic independence,
- v. Admiration of one's physique,
- vi. Hyperactivity resulting sometimes to juvenile delinquency e.g. stealing, pick-pocketing, abortion, teenage pregnancy and baby-dumping.
- vii. Assumption of masculine/feminine roles.

The role of ICT in Engineering Functional Education for the Adolescent

The ICT as a new and sophisticated technology plays the following roles in ensuring functional education for the adolescent:

1. Computer education
2. Development and acquisition of skills
3. Self-reliance
4. Browsing the Internet
5. Using E-mail

6. Independent and Across-school collaborative studies
7. Online library studies
8. Online filling and submission of forms
9. Use of computer packages
10. Creativity
11. Software management
12. Knowledge of computer diseases, preventive and curative measures.

1. Computer Education

The ICT as a new and sophisticated technology which has brought the world into a global village provides computer education for the adolescent. Computer education is the acquisition of requisite knowledge and skills in computer. It is the training in computer to enable the trainee to use the acquired knowledge to operate computer on daily basis to solve problems or perform certain tasks. Computer education is beyond typing on the keyboard and using the printer to produce paper copies. Generally, computer education involves reading computer/ pamphlets, textbooks, Journals and magazines, discussing computer with friends, joining computer clubs and associations, attending computer seminars, workshops and conferences, attending computer hardware, software and book exhibitions etc (Nwosu, .2002). The ICT through computer education provides the requisite knowledge and skills for the adolescent and makes him a productive member of the society. Once the adolescent is productive and becomes a wage-earner, he shuns , social vices and delinquent acts associated with teenage age. Such delinquent acts according to Child (1977) are: truancy, taking and driving a car, vandalism, stealing trespassing, sex misdemeanours e.g. in the case of girls, prostitution.

2. Development and Acquisition of Skills

Through ICT, the adolescent develops and acquires a lot of skills in computer, Internet and e-mail to mention but a few. These are the skills needed in the labour marketed and productive sectors of the economy in contemporary times. The Danish Ministry of Education (2001), point out that, knowledge and skills in computer are the key factors for production in the 21st century. This goes to stress that the ICT skills and competencies are imperative for the adolescent, so as to enable him or her face the challenges of the competitive labour market. The world of work today both in public and private sectors is technology-based. The advanced and sophisticated technology have forced businesses, organizations, industries and institutions to redesign and redefine their operational technologies and management. For instance, bank transactions are getting more and more complex with the use of Automated Teller Machine (ATM). For the adolescent to work in the bank these days, he must show the skills and dexterity in using ICT resources such as the Internet, e-mail, computer hardware and software e.g. diskettes, flash drives and CD-Rom to mention but a few.

3. Self-Reliance

Self-reliance means self-employment or self-economic sustainability. The ICT provides the requisite knowledge and productive skills for self-reliance. The New Lexicon Webster's Dictionary defines skill as, "the ability to do something well, especially as a result of long practical experience". The acquisition of requisite skills, knowledge and technical know-how in ICT is a

means of increasing the productive power of the adolescent. With the skills and competencies of ICT, where he does not get the white-collar job, he can be self-employed. This will inevitably reduce all types of unemployment VIZ: structural unemployment, frictional/technological unemployment, casual unemployment, disguised unemployment and cyclical unemployment to the barest minimum. Self reliance through ICT will also go a long way in reducing social vices and delinquent acts, such as stealing, pick-pocketing, abortion, teenage pregnancy and baby dumping to its lowest ebb. The National Policy on Education (FRN, 2004) recognizes self-reliance through ICT, vocational and technical skills.

4. Browsing the Internet

The Internet which is an acronym for International Network for Communications has brought the world into a global village. There are millions of computer networks and Web sites connected to the Internet. A lot of things can be done on the Internet viz: e-mail, e-commerce/internet marketing, e-banking, library visits, downloading of files, finding free software applications, teleconference, joining of news groups and collaborative studies to mention but a few. An adolescent who is skillful and competent in the use of ICT facilities can browse, access or cruise the internet to read a lot of books and newspapers. There are media houses such as the Cable Network News (CNN). This day and Vanguard newspapers etc that have their websites where one can read news on daily basis[^]. For instance, this day newspapers can-be read at www.thisdayonline.com. While the Vanguard newspaper can be read at <http://www.vanguardngr.com>. All these prepare and build the adolescent for the socio-psychology of work, and to be a productive member of the society.

5. Using E-mail

E-mail stands for electronic mail. It is the most popular internet service. Letters, and binary attachments such as pictures, sounds, graphics, files and programmes can be sent from one computer to another. E-mail is the electronic version of the post office box. In using e-mail as one of the ICT resources, the adolescent learns how to send mails to his friends, parents, siblings and to his school teachers to solve academic problems. He or she can also send fax messages. A fax is a graphic image that is digitalized and sent over regular telephone lines using devices called modems. He or she can also send non-text materials such as pictures, graphs, images and sounds using what is called multi-purpose internet mail extensions (MIME). The use of these ICT resources helps to keep the body and mind of the adolescent together. He becomes a positive thinker with bright futures rather than indulging in delinquent acts that are likely to ruin his future.

Independent and Across-School Collaborative Studies,

With the ICT skills and competence, the adolescent can study independently in the Internet or can join in the across-school collaborative studies. This is because the ICT has brought schools connected to the Internet into a global dot. He or she can carry out an assignment, project, or research topics given him or her with other students in various geographical distances without physically traveling to those schools. In this way, he widens his intellectual horizon and shares ideas with relative ease. He or she can also make comparative analysis of the work done and draws inference or conclusion. In this way, the ICT increase importance within the school,

curriculum. It supports teaching and learning though remains a subject in its own right. By implication, within the school curriculum, the ICT enhances the learning experiences of the learner's.

7. Online Library Studies

The Library is the greatest reservoir of knowledge. With the ICT, library can be visited online. Books of various sizes, journals, magazines, newspapers, etc can be read online. They can also be downloaded and printed out. The adolescent who is computer literate can visit the library in the internet. He or she brows and collects huge amount of information from books software materials, graphics and non-graphics materials. He or she can visit, any of the four major parts of library Viz: circulation department, reference department, reserve and serial section for any information needed. As he or she reads through the pages of books, he or she increases his reading skills and widens his or her intellectual horizon.

8. Online Filling and Submission of Forms.

With the ICT skills and competencies) the adolescent can fill and submit forms online. For instance, W AEC forms, NECO NBTE and JAMB forms can be filled and submitted online. All he needs to so is to access the website of the examination body e.g JAMB by taking the following steps:

- A. Access the website
- b. Click on tabs relevant to forms and they will display all forms on the Screen.
- C. Fill the form
- d. Click submit to submit the form- for you.

This saves the time, trouble and expense of traveling to the examination body offices. Also, it reduces the risk of accidents and other mishaps on the road.

9. Creativity

The ICT provides for creative and entrepreneurial skills. A lot of graphic designs, charts images and scenes can be created using the computer. The input devices for computer graphics are the mouse, touch pad, keyboard, and joystick: There is need to train the adolescent to the acquire the creative skills. He can be creating a lot of designs for companies like coca-cola and the Nigerian Breweries (NBL). He can also *be* creating cartons and comics for media houses, academic and allied institutions. He can as well advance by making use of graphics software viz: Computer-Aided Design (CAD) and computer Aided Manufacture (CAM). All these go to make the adolescent a creative mind, a productive member of the society; and a wage-earner. By using ICT skills and dexterity in creating graphics and designs, he would not have time for social vices such as stealing, sexual day-dreaming, fun-seeking, dating and multiple mating, abortion, teenage pregnancy and baby-dumping. In the words of Ekwem (2001), serious emphasis on word processing, telecommunication equipment and competencies is the only force that can help the nation in the spread of knowledge for creativity and productivity.

10. Use of Computer Packages

The ICT exposes the adolescent to the knowledge and skills for using various computer packages or software. Some of the packages as indicated in Sanders and Stanley (1980) are:

- A. Word Processing Software e.g Microsoft word

- B. Accounting Software e.g Excel
- C. Engineering software e.g Auto CAD
- D. Graphics software e.g Corel Draw
- E. Anti-virus software e.g Norton etc.

If the adolescent can operate the computer and use the packages effectively, he becomes a hot-cake in the labour market. For instance, if he can show skills and dexterity in the use of word processing and accounting software, he can be employed as a clerk/ cashier in any of the business and organizations, banks, industries and institutions.

11. Software Management

Software management is one of the essential elements of ICT. Software is a collective name for all the programs that have been written for the computer to enable it handle problems in various fields. Software management is the caring, organization and the management of software for recall or retrieval of information at all times. Various kinds of software are: diskettes, flash drives, CD-ROM, tapes, punch cards, audio cards and electronic spreadsheet (Nwosu, 2002). Others are word processing software, accounting software, communication software to mention but a few. If the adolescent as a young school learner gets a job and he is able to keep and manage the software effectively, he cannot be thrown out of office or dismissed as a result of incompetence. He will continue to work, earn his wages and enjoy job security.

12. Knowledge of Computer Disease Preventive and Curative Measures.

Through the ICT, the adolescent becomes aware of various types of computer diseases, and their preventive and curative measures. Computer diseases are the diseases which infect and disturb the normal functioning of the computer system. Sometimes, they destroy the data stored in the computer. Examples are virus, bugs, clashes and Trojans to mention but a few. With the knowledge and skills of ICT, the adolescent should be able to install ant-virus software such as PC-Cillin, MacAfee, Dr. Solomon's and Norton's anti-viruses so as to check virus infection in the computer.

Recommendations

For functional, self-reliant or self-sustainable education for the adolescent using ICT, it is recommended as follows:

1. That the government should make information and communication Technology (ICT) a compulsory subject in all schools and colleges.
2. The government should procure and equip the schools with computer and its accessories for effective teaching and learning of ICT as a subject.
3. The government should call on installation and Maintenance Company known as the internet service provider (ISP) to construct ICT centers, websites and networks in all schools for accessibility of information in the internet at all times.
4. National Competition in the form of essays, quizzes and project on ICT should be organized annually; and prizes and award should be given to befitting students.
5. The National Directorate of Employment (NDE) should procure computers and give reasonable discount to young school-leavers who want to purchase the computers for self-employment. This will go a long way to getting them employed and to

ameliorating the problems e.g stealing, robbery, abortion, pregnancy and by dumping associated with adolescents. .

6. There should be government subsidy on ICT materials such as the computer and terminals, scanner and printers etc. since the ICT provides both entrepreneurial and productive skills. As a self- reliant person, the adolescent will learn more about microeconomics. Consequently, he will gain insight into financial relationships. of employers in the private sectors and the government. This will motivate him to go into macro-economics instead being a sleep-about, a fun-seeker or one who indulges in sexual day-dreaming.
7. Seminars, conferences and workshops should be organized from time to time to enable the adolescent update his knowledge in ICT and to keep on with the modern global trends in technology.
8. Finally, the government should encourage indigenous authors to write books on ICT as a subject in the school curriculum. This should be done by given the author's research allowances and incentives; and by recommending their textbooks to be used as learning materials in schools and colleges.

CONCLUSION

Functional education is the education for self-reliance or self sustainability. It is the education that enables one to use his creative ingenuity, technical skills, abilities and competencies to be self-reliant. It is the education that makes a person an efficient and creative producer rather than parasitic consumer. The ICT is a technology which provides for both entrepreneurial and productive skills and has brought the world into a global village. It is therefore of paramount importance that the adolescent should learn it as a compulsory school subject so as to be a productive member of the society.

REFERENCES

Anyanwu, C.N (1987). *Developing Adult Education in Nigeria*. Ibadan: University Press.

- Berstecher, D. (1985). *Education and Rural Development*. Paris: Evans.
- Child, D. (1977). *Psychology and the Teacher*. London: Holt.
- Danish Ministry of Education (2001). *The Development of Education Denmark: Danish Research and Development Center for Adult Education*.
- Ekwem, A. (2001, May 29:63) Experts Advocate Internet Protocol (IP). *The Guardian*.
- Fanyisetan, B and Pebbly, A.R. (1989). Pre-material Sexuality in Urban Nigeria *Journal, of studies in family planning*. 20 (6), 343-345.
- Federal Republic of Nigeria (2004). *National Policy on Education*. Lagos: NERDC Press.
- Hall, J; and Smith, J. (1991). *Information Technology For ALL*. England: McGraw-Hill.
- Hall, C.L. (1963). *Principles of Behaviour*. New York: Appleton-Century-Crofts New Lexicon Webster's Dictionary. Third Edition.
- Nwosu, S.E (2002). *Fundamentals of Computer Education and Educational Technology*. Enugu: Cedartop Pub.
- Sanders; D.H. and Stanley. J.B (1980) *Computers and Management in a changing society*. New York: Mcgraw-Hill
- Ukeje, B.O (1957). Nigerian Needs and Nigerian Education: A study of the critical Needs of an Emergent Nation and the Role of Education in meeting them. *A Report of Type C. Project*. Columbia: Columbia-University
- UNESCO (1964). Handbook on the organization and Financing of Adult Literacy and Adult Education Programmes in Africa. Proceedings of a Regional Conference on the planning and organization of literacy programmes in Africa. Abidjan 9th _ 14th March.
- Uzoigwe, C. U. (2001). Information Technologies Libraries: The Nigerian case. A conference *Paper Presented to the Nigeria Library Association*. Enugu: State Central Library, November, 20.